

A Study on the Mental Health and Self Confidence of B.Ed Students in Coimbatore District

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ABSTRACT

India is a very fast developing country of the world. After independence, it has recorded a remarkable progress in every field of life. In this train of progress, the role of education cannot be avoided. Since independence, many educational colleges and institutions have been established. But these colleges and institutions are not significant on the part of the teachers. The teachers trainees of present day are not knowing their role. In general, Teacher trainees are lack of mental health and self confidence and poor attitude towards teaching profession. So the investigator try to attempt in this present research study to inculcate mental health and self confidence for developing teaching competence among teacher trainees. Casual observations by the investigator of this paper as a teaching practice supervisors shows that many student teachers lack necessary ability to link theories learnt in class to classroom practice. This study will help teachers to understand how mental health and self confidence influences the processes of teaching and learning. This information is lacking in the literature and it is therefore not readily available to help inform educational improvement efforts that support better teaching practices and student performance.

The significance of this study lies in its practical application to the Diploma in teacher education programme. This study, using an experimental research model, provides a platform from which an exploration of these areas might begin. This study will help teachers to understand how mental health and self confidence influences the processes of teaching and learning. This information is lacking in the literature and it is therefore not readily available to help inform educational improvement efforts that support better teaching practices and student performance. This information will then be used to identify areas of relative strength and weakness in the pedagogy component of Professional Development and Experience subjects with a view to improving this component of the Course.

Keywords: Mental Health, Self-Confidence

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a key role in the development of a Nation. The word education has a very wide connotation. It is hard to define. According to Plato Education develops in the body and in the soul of the child all the beauty and perfection of which he is capable of "Education has to develop the physical and spiritual qualities of man to the full". Education is a life long process of development from infancy to modernity. It includes the effect of everything which influences the human personality.

Education gives instruction to persons. Psychology is centered on the behaviour of persons. During the Adolescence period, they are affected by many psychological factors. Adolescence is a span of growth and development. We can see rapid development of all the internal and external organ of the body. The psychological factors may affect their academic achievement. In this chapter the investigator deals with the topics such as the emergence of the problems, the need and scope of the study, significance of

the study, definition of the problems, delimitation of the problem etc., the investigator tries to give a bird eye view of the problem studied.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

"A STUDY ON THE MENTAL HEALTH AND SELF CONFIDENCE OF B.ED STUDENTS IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT"

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Serta Sandal, Shaba Due, and Bhatia Bhavnagar (2011) studied the mental health of adolescents with specific reference to Integration of personality. The sample selected for the present study comprised of 120, adolescents. The sample was selected from Sash Aswan public school, Raipur city Rajasthan). Mental health inventory (M.H.I.) by Jag dish and Srivastava, A.K. a standardized tool was used for data collection. Major findings of the study were: 1. the percentage on integration of personality (IP) which means

balance of psychic force in the individual and includes the ability to understand and to share other people's emotions, the ability to concentrate at work and have interest in several activities. 2. Girls were leading in this category than boys as the girls have more patience, tolerance, emotional stability and more well adjustable than boys.

Sarah Base (2012) studied the gender and mental health a comparative study of teachers in primary schools and colleges. A sample of 225 primary school teachers and 150 college teachers from Rohilkhand region was selected using multi-stage random sampling technique. The mental health inventory (MHI) developed by Jadish and Srivastava was the tool used. Major findings of the study were: 1. College teachers have significantly better mental health than primary school teachers. 2. Male teachers working in primary schools as well as colleges have significantly higher level of mental health than their female counterparts.

METHOD OF THE STUDY

The present study attempts to find out the mental health and self-confidence of B.Ed. students. Since the problem is concerned with "Survey" type, the investigator has selected the normative survey method for conducting the study.

The word 'survey' indicates the gathering of the data regarding current conditions. The word "normative" is used because surveys are frequently made for the purpose of ascertaining which is the normal or typical condition or practice. "Normative Survey" is applied in order to suggest the two closely related aspects of study. The descriptive or normative survey method of educational research is very common. It is that method of investigation which attempts to describe and interpret what exists at present in the form of conditions, practices, processes, attitudes, beliefs etc. It is concerned with the phenomena that are typical of the normal conditions. It is an organized attempt to analyze, interpret, report the present status of social institution, group or area.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Ten Colleges are selected through stratified random sampling technique. The sample for the present study consisted of 360 B.Ed. students in Coimbatore district. The students of both sexes coming from both rural and urban areas were included in the study.

TOOL USED IN THE STUDY

The data are essential for carrying out research investigation. The data are collected with the help of the special apparatus called as tools. The success of a research must be received by selecting a proper tool for the research. So, that the investigator used the following tool i.e. mental health and self-confidence.

- Mental Health by **Crowther, Rosalind (2004)**
- Self-confidence Inventory by **Martos Tamas (2010)**

DATA COLLECTION

In Coimbatore district, the investigator selected ten self-financed colleges using stratified random sampling technique. A set of management students from each college was selected in a random manner. Thus the researcher used stratified random sampling technique for collection of data from the vast area of Coimbatore district.

THE STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Suitable descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used in the interpretation of the data to draw a more meaningful picture of results from the collected data in the present study from the following statistical measures were used.

- Mean
- Standard deviation
- 'T' test
- 'F' test

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

MENTAL HEALTH

- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the mental health of B.Ed. students in respect to their gender.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the mental health of B.Ed. students in respect to their locality of college.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the mental health of B.Ed. students in respect to their type of family.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the mental health of B.Ed. students in respect to their medium of instruction.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the mental health of B.Ed. students in respect to their parent's educational qualification.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the mental health of B.Ed. students in respect to their family annual income.

SELF-CONFIDENCE

- It is found that, there is a significant difference in the self-confidence of B.Ed. students in respect to their gender.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the self-confidence of B.Ed. students in respect to their locality of college.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the self-confidence of B.Ed. students in respect to their type of family.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the self-confidence of B.Ed. students in respect to their medium of instruction.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the self-confidence of B.Ed. students in respect to their parent's educational qualification.
- It is found that, there is no significant difference in the self-confidence of B.Ed. students in respect to their family annual income.
- It is found that, there is a significant relationship between self-confidence and mental health of B.Ed. students.

CONCLUSION

The statistical and subsequent analysis revealed that mental health among the B.Ed. students is enhanced through the implementation of self-confidence. The enhancement in level of self-confidence and mental health observed in assessment scores is due to the survey method. There is a positive correlation between Self-confidence and Mental health in all the assessments. The tools evolved to enhance the mental health using self-confidence is found to be effective.

REFERENCE

- [1] **Jahoda, M. (1978)** current concepts of the mental health. Basic Books, New York.
- [2] **Narayana Rao, S. (1997)**. Educational Psychology. Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi.
- [3] **Padus, Emrik (1995)**. The complete guide to your emotions and your health (Revised Edition) – Hundreds of proven techniques to harmobize mind & body for happy, healthy living. Rajendra Publishing House Private Ltd., Bombay.
- [4] **Sarafino, Edward P. (1990)** Health Psychology, Biopsychosocial interactions. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- [5] **Sharma, R.A. (2002)**. Fundamental of Educational Research. International Publishing House, India.
- [6] **Steeve, Morgan. (1983)**. Community & Mental Health : Practical approaches to long term problems. Plenum Press, New York.
- [7] **Warr, P.B. (1987)** work, unememployment and Mental Health Oxford University Press, Oxford.

